

Inadequate data hampers attempts to understand and tackle food insecurity in the UK

Summary

Rising food bank use in the UK suggests growing levels of food insecurity. However, a representative measure of food insecurity was not routinely collected in the UK until 2019, over a decade after the start of sharply increasing food bank demand. In the absence of historical data on food insecurity and hunger it is necessary to use proxy indicators to understand the growth of insecure access to food in the 21st century. Economic indicators show that the economy's poor overall growth since 2005 has disproportionately impacted the poorest UK households, likely increasing vulnerability and incidence of food insecurity. Our analysis suggests that this vulnerability was exacerbated for some by welfare reforms and has been further intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic. Diet-related health outcomes suggest that poor diet quantity/quality has often been inequitably distributed across socioeconomic status. Family Resource Survey (FRS) data shows clearly that food insecurity is high in the UK population. It is paramount that the government continues to include food insecurity questions in the FRS, and adds additional questions on food bank use to improve understanding of the relationship between food insecurity and food bank use. Better data is crucial to effective evidence-based action to address the growing crisis of food insecurity.

Policy recommendations

- Continue to commit to annual monitoring of food insecurity in the Family Resource Survey; however adopt both a 12 month and 30 day time period of food insecurity measurement to improve comparability of data.
- Collect specific data to measure the prevalence of food insecurity in children.
- Re-assess the five week wait for Universal Credit, the two-child limit and the benefit cap in the social security system in light of growing evidence showing the detrimental effects of these policies on households.
- Assess and address in-work poverty as a driver of food insecurity risk.
- Assess the relationship between poor quality, expensive housing and rising food insecurity, and consider introducing measures to limit the cost of renting in the private sector and prioritise regeneration of social housing stock.
- Action to address the immediate needs of a food insecure population should not promote food-based solutions only. The wider, socio-economic determinants of food insecurity need to be identified and addressed.

Challenge

'Food security' means having access at all times to enough food that is both sufficiently varied and culturally appropriate to sustain an active and healthy life. The inclusion of the USDA Adult Food Insecurity Module in 2019-20 [Family Resource Survey](#) (FRS) is the first large, nationally representative attempt to measure food insecurity and hunger in the UK. On the eve of the COVID-19 pandemic, 8% of UK households were food insecure, with low (4%) or very low (4%) household food security. A further 6% of the population lived in households that were marginally food secure. Ethnicity, age, location, and benefit status all influenced incidence (Supp.1). [\[Links to the supplementary data are at the end of the brief.\]](#)

Prior to the 2019-20 FRS, routine collection of large-scale data on the prevalence of food insecurity in the UK was very limited. This lack of formal data imposes a reliance on proxy markers of food insecurity to give an approximate indication of the prevalence of food insecurity or the prevalence of the conditions associated with increased likelihood of food insecurity.

Method

To identify proxy markers to approximate the prevalence of historical food insecurity in the UK a rapid evidence synthesis review of the existing literature was conducted. Published manuscripts, grey literature, UK Government data resources and consultation with stakeholders were employed to select candidate longitudinal proxy indicators.

Results

FOOD BANK DATA: The experience of food bank users can provide an important insight into the drivers of food insecurity and can therefore serve as a proxy indicator. Food bank data is also uniquely useful as it has been reported longitudinally since food bank networks and usage increased circa 2005. Despite issues with the granularity of food bank statistics - e.g. identifying unique users - the data suggest that the prevalence of food insecurity in the UK has increased significantly since 2005, particularly post-recession and during the COVID-19 pandemic (Supp.2). However, food bank data gives an incomplete indication of the [experiential range of food insecurity](#). Most food bank users fall towards the

severe end of the food insecurity scale – a significant proportion of food bank users are [destitute](#) – and therefore must be considered a **non-representative subset of the food insecure population**. Mild and moderate food insecurity – e.g. worry over capacity to reliably obtain food and compromising on the quality of food – are associated with profound negative effects on mental and physical health and are likely under-represented in food bank data. The majority of those in need may not access food bank provision and will therefore also remain unacknowledged.

ECONOMIC MARKERS: Poverty and associated economic markers can be considered indicative of a landscape in which there is an increased risk of food insecurity for many in a population.

The [Joseph Rowntree Foundation](#) considers poverty trends to be driven primarily by four factors: earnings, employment rate, housing costs and benefits. Since 2005, there has been no sustained period during which all four drivers were positively trending in a direction that would protect living standards as the UK faced a period of relatively poor growth by historical standards. Crucially, the impacts of the recession and the COVID-19 pandemic, poor growth and stagnation shown in many economic markers have not been equitably distributed across the population.

Increases in living standards have been stagnant amongst the poorest households with those in the lowest 10th percentile seeing no increase in income for over eight years (Supp.3). Children are particularly affected by poverty due to stagnation in the real value of benefits and tax credits (Supp.4).

Child poverty was predicted to [continue to rise](#) even before the added impact of the pandemic.

Employment and income gains post-recession have been offset for many by a fall in value of working-age benefits and tax credits. [In-work poverty](#) has also increased – 58% of working households were living below the UK relative poverty line in 2017/18 compared to 37% in 1994/95 – and an increasing number of young adults are working in precarious, zero-hour jobs (Supp.5).

Significant changes in housing tenure and housing costs have also disproportionately affected low-income households, and younger adults in particular. Poorer households spend more of their income on housing than richer households (Supp. 6) and this [disparity has been increasing](#) since 2007/08. A shift in tenure to private rentals, particularly amongst [young adults in poverty](#), and a scarcity and rising cost of social housing, has resulted in a growing proportion of poorer households spending over a third of their income on housing.

Income stagnation in the poorest households in the wake of the recession coincided with rising food costs to reduce the affordability of food (Supp.7). Since food is often the only flexible item in a household budget, fluctuations in the cost of food, increased housing costs and reduced income will likely have reduced the amount and/or quality of food the poorest households could afford.

Changes in the UK economic landscape during and after the recession, accompanied by rising living costs, have undoubtedly put extra strain on low-income households, increasing the likelihood of poverty and food insecurity. However, these events have been significantly exacerbated by the welfare

reform policies since 2010. The retraction of the welfare state effectively shrank the social security safety net, increasing poverty among low income households. **The effects of welfare diversification, public spending cuts, benefit conditionality and benefit freezes, and a reduced real value of benefits have combined to reduce the incomes of those households already below and close to the poverty line – the unemployed or unable to work, the underemployed, those working on low paid or precarious contracts, those requiring disability support, households containing children – at a time of existing economic hardship, increasing vulnerability to food insecurity in those known to be disproportionately at risk** (Supp.8).

DIET-RELATED HEALTH MARKERS: Food insecurity is characterised by a reduction in the quantity and quality of food consumed. **Indicators of diet-related health outcomes suggest a reduction in UK diet quantity/quality since 2005.** For example, hospital admissions with malnutrition have increased dramatically, in both older and younger age groups (Supp.9). Comparatively low levels of food insecurity in older adults suggests reduced social care provision may be a greater determinant of this increase – **mean per-person [social care spending in England](#) between 2009/10 and 2017/18 fell by 31.2% for those over 65 years.** Poor nutrition is also indicated by the reemergence of ‘Victorian Diseases’ – e.g. rickets, scurvy – long considered relics of an impoverished past (Supp.10).

The causes of diet-related disease are complex and diverse. However, evidence of socio-economic inequalities in their incidence suggests poverty, and by extension food insecurity, are key determinants. For example, obesity and dental health in children are clearly delineated by socio-economic status (Supp.11).

Conclusions

Quantitative estimates of food insecurity since 2005 have relied on a patchwork of data collected by third sector organisations and researchers. This evidence, combined with the rich and detailed qualitative first-hand accounts of those living with food insecurity, have provided an invaluable, but incomplete, insight into the prevalence of food insecurity in the UK. The use of proxy indicators to estimate the longitudinal prevalence of food insecurity is necessitated by the historic absence of a formalised measurement.

It is clear that food bank data, wider economic and social welfare provision markers, and nutrition-related health outcomes are not sufficient to give a comprehensive and clear indication of food security prevalence. However, it is possible to speculate that food insecurity has increased since the early 21st century, at least towards the most severe end of the food insecurity scale as indexed by food bank data. It is also clear that a combination of economic and socio-political factors over the last 15 to 20 years, particularly post-recession, have created conditions in which the risk of food insecurity is likely to have increased for the poorest and most vulnerable UK households. The available data also strikingly illustrates the difficulty of accounting for the full spectrum of food insecurity experience in the absence of a direct measure.

The adoption of the USDA Food Security Measurement Module should not be considered a perfect solution to a lack of food insecurity data in the UK. The Module, by only measuring food insecurity at a household level, fails to account for individual experience, including that of children and, by measuring food insecurity over 30 days rather than a 12 month period, may underestimate food insecurity and has limited comparability with other studies. There is already sufficient evidence to show food insecurity is a problem for a sizable proportion of the UK population. Therefore, the focus of efforts should be to target resources on addressing the issue rather than delay response to permit standardised measurement. Further, targeting food insecurity in isolation may result in food-based only solutions (e.g. food charity, redistribution of surplus food)

and neglect of the wider overarching societal and economic problems, particularly the government's response to alleviate poverty and the causes of poverty.

More information

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The supplementary information for this brief can be found here:

<https://policyhub.n8agrifood.ac.uk/supplementary-data/>

You can also scan this QR code to access the supplementary data.

A related paper by the same authors 'Proxy longitudinal indicators of household food insecurity in the UK' can be found as part of the Emerald Open Research N8 AgriFood Collection here:

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